

Temporal Evolution of Engagement with edX MOOCs: A Case Study at the Universitat Politècnica de València

Ignacio Despujol Zabala^{1[0000-0003-2776-1638]}, Carlos Turró Ribalta^{2[0000-0002-3840-9405]},
Jaime Busquets Mataix

^{1,2,3,4} Universitat Politècnica de València, Camino de Vera sn 46021 Valencia, Spain
ndespujol@asic.upv.es¹, turro@cc.upv.es², busquets@asic.upv.es³

Abstract. While MOOC enrollments and media attention have declined in recent years, this study investigates whether this trend reflects a genuine loss of public interest or a shift in media focus. We hypothesize that MOOCs remain valuable, particularly within specific communities. To explore this, we analyze the sustained engagement of the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) community with edX MOOCs through an internal coupon initiative, extending a program originally launched during the 2020 COVID-19 lockdown. Examining data from November 2020 to February 2024, we assess course requests, completions, and university credit validations. Our findings reveal a persistent and, in the last two years, increasing interest in MOOCs within the UPV community, particularly for job-relevant skills like Excel, Linux, project management, and programming. Over the study period, 5,342 users claimed 13,197 coupons, resulting in 4,734 course completions and 1,267 university credit validations, totaling 45,063 validated credit-hours. With an overall completion rate of approximately 36%, this study demonstrates the enduring value of MOOCs for academic and professional development within the UPV community, suggesting that internal initiatives can maintain and even enhance engagement despite broader trends.

Keywords: MOOC, University, use case.

1 Introduction

The emergence of Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) in the early 2010s was announced as a disruptive innovation in education, promising to democratize learning and provide access to high-quality courses for anyone, anywhere (Pappano, 2012). Platforms like Coursera, edX, and Udacity captured widespread media attention as they enrolled millions of students across the globe, attracting both academic and corporate partnerships (Rodríguez, 2012). However, over the past decade, the initial excitement surrounding MOOCs has waned, with declining enrollment numbers and a noticeable decrease in media coverage. Critics have pointed to challenges such as low completion rates, limited interaction, and questions about their long-term scalability and sustainability as reasons for this decline (Reich & Ruipérez-Valiente, 2019).

Despite this perceived downturn, MOOCs have not disappeared. Instead, they have evolved, finding new niches and applications beyond their original vision of universal

education. Specifically, MOOCs are increasingly being used by institutions and organizations to address targeted learning needs, such as professional upskilling, corporate training, and academic credit integration (Otto et al., 2021).

This paper aims to shed light on whether the decline in public enthusiasm for MOOCs reflects a genuine loss of interest or simply a shift in focus. By examining the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) community's sustained engagement with MOOCs offered through the edX platform, we intend to demonstrate that MOOCs can remain a valuable tool for lifelong learning when implemented within a well-structured institutional framework.

1.1 What has happened to MOOCs?

The initial wave of enthusiasm for MOOCs was fueled by their potential to revolutionize education on a global scale. Early studies highlighted their ability to reach millions of learners, provide access to world-class instructors, and foster self-paced learning for individuals who might otherwise lack access to formal education (Daniel, 2012). Platforms such as Coursera, edX, and Udacity quickly gained prominence, forming partnerships with top universities and corporations to offer free or low-cost courses (Shah, 2020). However, the early promise of MOOCs was tempered by several challenges, including low completion rates, limited interaction between instructors and learners, and questions about their pedagogical effectiveness. For example, Jordan (2014) identified an average MOOC completion rate of less than 15%, raising concerns about the ability of MOOCs to deliver meaningful educational outcomes at scale.

By the mid-2010s, critiques of MOOCs began to dominate the discourse. Scholars such as Kovanović et al. (2015) argued that MOOCs were failing to democratize education as initially promised, primarily benefiting learners who were already highly educated and motivated. Additionally, the focus of many MOOC providers shifted from free access to monetized models, such as paid certificates and corporate training programs, leading to accusations that MOOCs were abandoning their original mission of open access. This shift coincided with a decline in media coverage and public interest, fueling the perception that MOOCs were a passing trend rather than a lasting innovation (Reich & Ruipérez-Valiente, 2019).

However, recent research suggests that this narrative may be overly simplistic. While MOOCs have not fulfilled their initial vision of universal education, they have found success in more specialized contexts. For instance, MOOCs have been effectively used for professional development, offering courses in high-demand fields such as data science, programming, and project management. Emanuel (2020) has highlighted the potential of MOOCs to support lifelong learning, particularly when integrated with institutional or corporate initiatives. In these contexts, MOOCs demonstrate higher completion rates and greater learner satisfaction, suggesting that their value lies in targeted applications rather than mass adoption.

The COVID-19 pandemic further underscored the potential of MOOCs as a tool for remote learning and skill development. During the global lockdowns of 2020, MOOC platforms experienced a resurgence of interest, with millions of learners enrolling in courses to acquire new skills or adapt to changing job markets. At the same time, many universities and organizations adopted MOOCs as part of their emergency response strategies, leveraging them to supplement traditional education and training. For example, Shah (2021) reported a significant increase in MOOC enrollments during the pandemic, with platforms like Coursera and edX experiencing record growth.

2 Post-Covid MOOC initiative in Universitat Politècnica de València

During the COVID-19 lockdown in 2020, Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) joined the Remote Access Program (RAP) initiative launched by edX, which aimed at providing free certificates for its MOOCs to partner communities. UPV developed a web-based mechanism to distribute course coupons to members of its own community. The coupons were used to waive course fees, and over 7,700 individuals, representing 23.4% of the UPV community, requested a total of 15,744 coupons and successfully obtained 5,202 certificates, resulting in a completion rate of 33%. This initiative proved to be highly successful in mitigating the effects of the lockdown (Despujol et al., 2022).

The UPV agreement with edX offers the possibility to have free coupons for UPV courses for on campus learners, so given that an automated web mechanism for coupon distribution had already been developed during the lockdown, and that the community members expressed their interest in obtaining certificates for these courses, the university decided to create a continuation initiative for UPV members.

To ensure the proper use of coupons and prevent misuse, UPV implemented a restriction that specified UPV-specific coupons could only be utilized within an edX account associated with an official email from the institution's domain. Given that the institution had the flexibility to request an unlimited number of coupons and that the coupons could only be used with an edX account linked to an institutional email address, a policy was put in place to allow users to request up to 5 coupons per email address, exclusively accepting email addresses from the upv.es domain.

This initiative already proved its value for UPV members in the first year, as stated by Despujol et al. (2023). However, given the decline in overall enrollments in MOOCs as a whole—from 40 million new learners signing up for a MOOC in 2021 as stated by Shah (2021) to 5 million learners in the main MOOC platforms in 2024, reported also by Shah (2024) on LinkedIn—and the decline in enrollments in UPV's MOOCs on edX, we wanted to know if the interest in MOOCs among UPV's community had faded or continued.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research questions

The object of this study is to evaluate if the UPV community has lost interest in getting free MOOC certificates.

The research questions are:

Q1: How have enrolments, passing rates and university credit demand evolved?

Q2: What subjects are most chosen by participants?

By addressing these research questions, we can gain insights into the interest of the university community in obtaining MOOC certificates for free and compare it with the general trend.

3.2 Type of study

This research has been conducted as a case study, enabling us to develop a comprehensive and nuanced understanding of a complex issue within its real-life context (Crowe et al. 2011). The case study approach is evaluative in nature as it involves analyzing the specific details and intricacies of the implementation process.

3.3 Data collection

The study utilized two data sources:

1. The databases of the coupon distribution tool for UPV courses, which consisted of three tables: "licencias" for coupon codes, "solicitudes" for coupon requests, and "cursos_aprobados" for a list of certificates obtained from UPV's edX courses (imported from edX.org).
2. The database used by UPV's administrative services to validate edX certificates and grant optional academic credit for MOOCs.

4 Results

4.1 General data

From November 11st, 2020, to February 23th, 2025, a total of 13,197 coupons were sent to members of UPV's community. These coupons were distributed among 5,342 different members. On average, each user received 2.47 coupons, with a maximum of 27 coupons requested by a single member. It is worth noting that seven members requested more than 20 coupons.

Table 1 provides a temporal distribution of the coupon demand (considering approximately 2 months of 2020 and 2 months in 2025).

Table 1. Temporal distribution of coupon demand

	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Coupons Requested	1661	1437	1559	4013	3763	764
Coupons per Month	997	120	130	334	314	424
Certificates per Month	155	71	61	106	114	138

The total number of certificates obtained using the coupons by 1,921 of these members is 1,674, resulting in a certification rate of 35.9% (considering the distribution of 13,197 coupons).

To determine the courses at UPV that generated the highest interest among the community we use data pertaining to obtained certificates. The coupons were used to obtain certificates for 128 of the courses offered by UPV on edX (almost all), but the top 10 courses accounted for 54.2% of the total certificates, while the top 20 courses represented 69.3% of all certificates obtained.

Table 2 presents details regarding the top 10 courses.

Table 2. Course certificates percentage

Course Code	Number of certificates	%	Accumulated %
xls101x	528	11,2%	11,2%
PY101x	385	8,1%	19,3%
LF-UPV-101x	311	6,6%	25,9%
WORD201X	278	5,9%	31,7%
XLS201x	265	5,6%	37,3%
IGP101.x	242	5,1%	42,4%
BI101x	196	4,1%	46,6%
XIS202x	125	2,6%	49,2%
SQL101x	122	2,6%	51,8%
MKTDIG102x	112	2,4%	54,2%

We can observe that the three Excel courses (codes XLS), ranging from introductory to advanced, comprise 19.4% of the total certificates. The “Introduction to Python” course (PY101x) represents 8.1% of the certificates and “Introduction to Linux” (LF-UPV-101x) contributes 6.6%, while the “Intermediate Word” course (WORD201X) accounts for 5.9% of the certificates. “Introduction to Project Management” (IGP101.x) contributes 5.1% and the “Search in Internet” course (BI101x) accounts for 4.1%. Additionally,

the “Introduction to SQL” (SQL101x) course and “Digital Marketing Fundamentals” (MKTDIG102x) contribute 2.6% and 2.4% of the certificates, respectively.

If we examine the temporal evolution of the different courses, we can see a slight decline in certification for Excel courses over the years, a significant growth in Linux course enrollments (which ranks first in 2024 and 2025), and a substantial growth in Introduction to Python enrollments (which ranks second in 2025).

4.2 University credit recognition

All bachelor's programs offered by the University include a percentage of optional credits in their curriculum (credits that can be achieved by participating in different activities instead of taking a regular course), and UPV recognizes MOOC certificates as a valid method to obtain these credits since 2019. Students have pursued these optional university credits by utilizing 1,267 MOOC certificates, resulting in a cumulative total of 45,063 credit-hours. 10 of the 13 schools of the University have recognized credit-hours.

Table 3. Temporal distribution of certified credit-hours

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Credit-Hours	524	3351	7328	4820	11326	16638	1076
Credit-Hours per Month	131	279	611	402	944	1387	598

The most sought-after courses were Introduction to Linux, Excel Fundamentals, and Search Internet, following a similar pattern to the certificates obtained.

5 Discussion

Regarding the first research question, the collected data indicates that the UPV community maintains a continued interest in MOOCs, with a decline after the lockdown period but with renewed interest in recent years. The same pattern is observed with the use of MOOCs to obtain university credit. In terms of pass rate, the completion rate is 35.9%, which is significantly higher than the average MOOC completion rate reported in previous studies.

Responding to the second research question, the analysis reveals that the most sought-after subjects primarily revolve around job-specific skills, including Excel, project management, programming, and operating systems.

6 Conclusions

The data reveals that the UPV community shows renewed interest in obtaining free MOOC certificates, particularly in job-specific skills and programming courses, which differs from the general trend observed in overall MOOC enrollment.

The authors suggest that the loss of media attention to MOOCs may be an important factor contributing to the shrinking enrollments globally, while targeted institutional initiatives like UPV's can maintain engagement.

This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on the relevance of MOOCs by presenting evidence of their sustained value within a specific community. In doing so, it highlights the potential for targeted institutional initiatives to counteract the broader decline in MOOC engagement and demonstrates the enduring role of MOOCs in academic and professional development.

References

1. Alraimi, K. M., Zo, H., & Ciganek, A. P.: Understanding the MOOCs continuance: The role of openness and reputation. *Computers & Education*, 80, 28–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.08.006> (2015).
2. Crowe, S., Cresswell, K., Robertson, A., Huby, G., Avery, A., & Sheikh, A.: The case study approach. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 11(1), 100. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2288-11-100> (2011).
3. Daniel, J.: Making sense of MOOCs: Musings in a maze of myth, paradox, and possibility. *Journal of Interactive Media in Education*, 2012(3), Art. 18. <https://doi.org/10.5334/2012-18> (2012)
4. Despujol, I., Castañeda, L., & Turró, C.: MOOCs as a massive learning resource for a Higher Education Community. The Universitat Politècnica de València experience using the EdX remote access program. *Education and Information Technologies*, 27(9), 12999–13020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11140-2> (2022).
5. Despujol, I., Turró, C., & Busquets, J.: Post-pandemic use of edX MOOCs by the Universitat Politècnica de València Community. 2023 IEEE Learning with MOOCs (LWMOOCs), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LWMOOCs58322.2023.10305902> (2023).
6. Ebben, M., & Murphy, J. S.: Unpacking MOOC scholarly discourse: A review of nascent MOOC scholarship. *Learning, Media and Technology*, 39(3), 328–345. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17439884.2013.878352> (2014).
7. Emanuel, E. J.: The inevitable reimagining of medical education in the digital age. *Academic Medicine*, 95(12), 1795–1798. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000003608> (2020).
8. Hew, K. F., & Cheung, W. S.: Students' and instructors' use of massive open online courses (MOOCs): Motivations and challenges. *Educational Research Review*, 12, 45–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.edurev.2014.05.001> (2014).
9. Hollands, F. M., & Tirthali, D.: MOOCs: Expectations and reality. Full Report. Center for Benefit-Cost Studies of Education, Teachers College, Columbia University. (2014).
10. Jordan, K.: Initial trends in enrolment and completion of massive open online courses. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 15(1), 133–160. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v15i1.1651> (2014).

11. Kovanović, V., Joksimović, S., Gašević, D., Siemens, G., & Hatala, M.: What public media reveals about MOOCs: A systematic analysis of news reports. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 46(3), 510–527. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjet.12277> (2015).
12. Margaryan, A., Bianco, M., & Littlejohn, A.: Instructional quality of massive open online courses (MOOCs). *Computers & Education*, 80, 77–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2014.08.005> (2015).
13. Otto, D., Bollmann, A., Becker, S., & Sander, K.: It's the learning, stupid! Discussing the role of MOOCs for employee development in organizations. *International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 22(1), 1-24. (2021)
14. Pappano, L.: The Year of the MOOC. *The New York Times*. <https://www.nytimes.com/2012/11/04/education/edlife/massive-open-online-courses-are-multiplying-at-a-rapid-pace.html> (accessed 21 February 2025). (2012).
15. Reich, J., & Ruipérez-Valiente, J. A.: The MOOC pivot. *Science*, 363(6423), 130–131. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aav7958> (2019)
16. Shah, D.: By the numbers: MOOCs in 2020. Class Central. Retrieved from <https://www.classcentral.com/report/mooc-stats-2020/> (accessed 21 January 2025). (2020).
17. Shah, D.: By the numbers: MOOCs in 2021. Class Central. Retrieved from <https://www.classcentral.com/report/mooc-stats-2021/> (accessed 21 January 2025). (2021).
18. Shah, D.: https://www.linkedin.com/posts/dhawals_remember-when-edx-and-coursera-were-neck-activity-7284650333954359296-hILD/ (accessed 22 February 2025). (2025).
19. Veletsianos, G., & Shepherdson, P.: A systematic analysis and synthesis of the empirical MOOC literature published in 2013–2015. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distributed Learning*, 17(2), 198–221. <https://doi.org/10.19173/irrodl.v17i2.2448> (2016).
20. Zheng, S., Rosson, M. B., Shih, P. C., & Carroll, J. M.: Understanding student motivation, behaviors, and perceptions in MOOCs. *Proceedings of the 18th ACM Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work & Social Computing*, 1882–1895. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2675133.2675217> (2015).